

UPBRINGING OF YOUTHS IN THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF THE EASTERN THINKERS

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Annotation

This article analyzes a number of works that are the scientific heritage of Eastern thinkers and the specific features of the views and ideas which aim to enrich the mental education of young people.

Keywords: Eastern thinkers, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, science, Abu Rayhan Beruni, scholars, Abu Ali ibn Sina, knowledge, wisdom, Yusuf Khas Khojib, “Qutadgu bilig”, universe, Bahauddin Naqshbandi, “Khilvat dar anjuman”, “Safar dar vatan”, Alisher Navoi, Abdulla Avloni, culture, enlightenment, method, training, debate.

Eastern thinkers paid special attention to questions of knowledge and human thinking. In particular, Abu Nasr al-Farabi considers the role of science in comprehending the secrets of being and nature by man as a decisive factor. In his opinion, the human body, brain and sense organs, if they existed at birth, are under the influence of mental and intellectual potential, spirituality, psyche, religious traditions, knowledge of the outside world, social environment. in the course of human relations.

According to Abu Nasr al-Farabi, the human mind is a product of its spiritual development. With the acquisition of knowledge, a person led the development, creation and science-based coverage of practical experience of owning people.

Continuing these thoughts of the scientist, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni formulates as follows: he accepts the truth.

The thinker also says that the acquisition of knowledge by people leads to the creation of new knowledge: “There are many sciences. They are having a good time and Turkish thoughts and memories will be multiplied if added. The fact that people are interested in science and respect the sciences and people of science is a sign of this success.¹

The respect of rulers for scientists will lead to the spread of various sciences.²

Abu Ali ibn Sina in his writings, commenting on the concept of knowledge, emphasizes that the deep acquisition of knowledge is wisdom: “Knowledge is the

¹ Beruniy Abu Rayhon. Selected works. Volume III. - Tashkent, State Publishing House, 1966, - 7 pages.

² Beruniy Abu Rayhon. Selected works. Volume II. - Tashkent, State Publishing House, 1965, - 125 p.

study of things with the help of the human mind. Knowledge is the perception of things. This is what the human mind must achieve without making mistakes or going astray. If the evidence is clear and the evidence is correct, then that is called wisdom.”³

“Kutadgu bilig” by Yusuf Khas Khodjib (“Knowledge leading to happiness”) is a description of the essence of knowledge, its significance in public life, its role in ensuring the improvement of man and its ability to eradicate evil. According to the thinker, knowledge is the key to the triumph of good deeds, which can even lead to paradise.

All good comes from the benefit of knowledge,
As if knowledge leads to heaven.

How truthful the scientist was when he expressed these thoughts. After all, after nine or ten centuries, a person can not only fly through the sky, but also conquer the universe.

Bahovuddin Nakshbandi in his teachings plays a leading role in directing the power of the saints for the benefit and development of knowledge and enlightenment. Therefore, knowledge is the path to liberation from oppression and heresy. The ideas put forward by the scientist “Hilvat dar anjuman” and “Safar dar vatan” indicate the expediency of acquiring existing knowledge through conversation and practice. After all, the knowledge that is formed in disputes and constant research is solid and thorough.

Alisher Navoi emphasizes the need for consistent, continuous acquisition of knowledge. Also, the study of science is a difficult task, and it is necessary to overcome some difficulties in its study.

Abdullah Avloni, on the other hand, about human perfection states: “Knowledge is the glory of this world and the glory of the future life. Science is a very sacred quality for a person, because science shows us our state and actions like a mirror, sharpens our mind and thoughts like a sword, and a person without knowledge is like a barren tree”⁴.

He also emphasizes that knowledge is the most effective means of saving man from ignorance: Today, our life, our goods, our happiness, our wealth, our livelihood, our generosity, our diligence, our peace and the life to come depend on science.⁵

There are several acceptable forms, methods and legal processes for observing the worldview of young people, including conversations on spiritual,

³ Ontology of Uzbek Pedagogy // Compilers: Khoshimov K., Safo Achil. - Tashkent, O'qituvchi, 1995, - 137 p.

⁴ Avloni A. Garden of morality and morality. - Tashkent, O'qituvchi, 1994, - p. 10.

⁵ Avloni A. Turkish gulistan or morality.- Tashkent, O'qituvchi, 1992, - pp. 22+23.

moral, socio-ideological, economic, legal, aesthetic and environmental issues, debates and discussions based on xs debates, practical exercises that encourage reflection as well as debate are considered more effective.

The functioning of the educational process, the organization of a systematic and clear social purpose, effective communication in this process, the ability to work in this process, relying on the existing world unity, which is considered effective. This information situation makes it possible to manage this or that social event from different points of view, to see the definition of the development file, to understand interdependence and interdependence, the need for each other.

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